

OPERATIVE TREATMENT OF VASOMOTOR RHINITIS IS TURBINOPLASTY, ADVANTAGES AND COMPLICATIONS OF TURBINOPLASTY

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Abstract. Turbinoplasty is the surgical procedure to reduce the size of turbinates within the nose. Surgery is usually indicated for patients who have a blocked nose due to enlarged inferior turbinates. In patients who have a blocked nose and the turbinates are seen to be large, commonly due to allergy or sinusitis, surgery to reduce their size may be an option.

Keywords: Turbinoplasty, Septoplasty, Endoscopic Sinus Surgery, Haemorrhage, Atrophic rhinitis, Adhesions.

ОПЕРАТИВНОЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ВАЗОМОТОРНОГО РИНИТА - ТУРБИНОПЛАСТИКА, ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА И ОСЛОЖНЕНИЯ ТУРБИНОПЛАСТИКИ

Аннотация. Турбинопластика — это хирургическая процедура по уменьшению размера носовых раковин в носу. Операция обычно показана пациентам с заложенностью носа из-за увеличенных нижних носовых раковин. У пациентов с заложенностью носа и большими носовыми раковинами, обычно из-за аллергии или синусита, может быть вариантом хирургическое вмешательство по уменьшению их размера.

Ключевые слова: турбинопластика, септопластика, эндоскопическая хирургия околоносовых пазух, кровотечение, атрофический ринит, спайки.

What is a Turbinoplasty?

Turbinoplasty is the surgical procedure to reduce the size of turbinates within the nose.

Typically a turbinoplasty means surgery on the inferior turbinates when they are large and blocking the nose. This commonly occurs due to allergy within the nose “allergic rhinitis” or sinusitis “chronic rhinosinusitis”.

The surgery is completed under a General Anaesthetic (an Anaesthetist will explain to you how this process will happen).

What are the indications for a Turbinoplasty?

Surgery is usually indicated for patients who have a blocked nose due to enlarged inferior turbinates. This may be particularly relevant in the case of severe snoring or “obstructive sleep apnoea”.

What happens before surgery?

You cannot eat or drink anything from 6 hours before your surgery. The anaesthetist will see you either in clinic days before the operation or on the day of surgery.

You may be asked to have routine blood tests taken prior to your surgery. If you take regular medication, some of them, in particular blood thinners may need to be stopped prior to your surgery.

How is it diagnosed?

Diagnosis is made through a combination of symptoms, examination of the nose and scans of the sinuses. In patients who have a blocked nose and the turbinates are seen to be large, commonly due to allergy or sinusitis, surgery to reduce their size may be an option. If use of a decongestant spray improves the breathing through the nose this would tend to suggest that surgery to reduce the size of the turbinates will be of assistance.

How long is the surgery?

The operation will take around one hour to complete but could be longer if it is completed with additional procedures (Septoplasty or Endoscopic Sinus Surgery). The entire process which includes pre-operation checks, anaesthesia and recovery can take several hours.

What are the risks?

Your ENT Surgeon will explain all the risks of surgery and answer any questions during your consultation. Small amounts of bleeding is expected in the first few days following surgery.

There will usually be some pain but this is typically relatively mild and manageable with simple pain killing tablets. It is best to avoid using aspirin for pain relief as this can cause bleeding

Complications:

1. Haemorrhage
2. Infection
3. Atrophic rhinitis
4. Adhesions

How long is the recovery?

Patients commonly go home the same day although on some occasions an admission overnight is necessary.

It is important to avoid physical contact with the nose, blowing your nose or any heavy physical activity in the first 1-2 weeks after surgery. You will be given a prescription for routine pain relief and commonly a saline rinse bottle which helps for gently washing clots and crusts from the nose after surgery.

Due to the swelling from the surgery, the nose may feel more blocked immediately after surgery. This should improve after 1-2 weeks. On average, expect to take around 7 days off school or work after surgery.

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